

High Resolution Postmortem Brain Imaging at 7 Tesla using Parallel Transmission and a Simple Set-Up

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Synopsis

In this work we present a simple set-up for high resolution postmortem imaging at ultra high field strength. The processed images have high, as well as homogeneous gray/white matter contrast over the whole brain. Additionally, during post-processing, the background signal of the fixation liquid is almost completely removed, allowing for an optimal image registration process after histological sectioning.

Purpose

High-resolution postmortem brain scans provide reslicable images of the brain tissue before permanent sectioning [1,2] and facilitate the visualizing of the microstructural neuroanatomy of the human brain. The histological processing inevitably introduces artifacts such as distortion and tearing of the brain tissue. This in turn introduces problems during the 3D reconstruction process. However, the histological sections can be nonlinear registered to an MRI, which serves as an undistorted frame of reference. To achieve an accurate registration result, the MR data has to have homogeneous and high gray/white matter contrast over the whole brain volume, and as less as possible background signal to aid the registration process. In this work, we describe a relatively simple experimental set-up for acquisition of such high resolution, high contrast, ex vivo brain images utilizing a 7T MR system with parallel transmission hardware.

Methods

The brain was placed in a custom-made coil shaped container filled with degassed 4% phosphat-buffered formaldehyde solution, and exposed to 500 mBar vacuum for 12h (20deg Celsius) to remove residual air bubbles. Figure 1 shows and describes the straightforward brain container assembly. All parts were obtained from an ordinary supply store.

Imaging was performed on a whole-body investigational MAGNETOM 7T scanner (Siemens AG, Healthcare Sector, Erlangen, Germany). Image homogenization was achieved by employing tailored, non-selective kT-points pulses (15 sub-pulses) [3]. The data were acquired using a head array coil with 32 receive and 8 transmit channels (Nova Medical, Wilmington, USA). To remove residual bias fields as well as unwanted background signal, T₁ quantification was performed on multi flip angle gradient echo images. The flip angle sampling was as follows: Minimum/maximum flip angle according to Olsson et. al. [4] (5 and 29 deg), Ernst angle (11 deg), and two additional flip angles in between (7 and 19 deg) , TR/TE: 20/5 ms, 200um isotropic resolution, 11h scan time per flip angle.

The residual transmit field bias of the kt pulse was removed by flip angle mapping using an additional AFI measurement [5] : 5mm isotropic resolution, 1 min scan time. The data were fitted to a modified Ernst equation [6], and images with optimized gray/white matter contrast were computed as follows:

$$I_{\text{opt}} = C * R_1 / M_0$$

with longitudinal relaxation rate R_1 , M_0 equilibrium magnetization, and a global scaling factor C . Finally, N4 bias field correction and image denoising was applied [7].

Results

In Figure 2 a comparison between a CP mode and full pTX acquisition is shown. Severe signal drop-outs appear in the brain when employing CP mode (Siemens Trueform) for imaging. In contrast, applying kt-points mitigates the B_0 and B_1 field inhomogeneities and removes those drop-outs completely over the whole brain volume (Figure 2 right, Figure 3). Fitting the multi flip angle data to the modified Ernst equation and applying equation 1 enhances the gray/white matter contrast and removes most of the background signal (Figure 4). In Figure 5 representative slices after bias field correction and image denoising on the optimized contrast image are shown. Anatomical details are visualized in great detail.

Discussion/Conclusion

In this work an easy to implement workflow for whole brain postmortem imaging on a 7T MR scanner is presented. Besides parallel transmission hardware, no specialized equipment such as dedicated RF coils are needed. Furthermore, a complicated and expensive fixation procedure of the postmortem brain (i.e. proton-free oil to eliminate background signal) is rendered unnecessary. Next, besides increasing the image resolution, multi parameter mapping [8] will be implemented to gain further neuroanatomic insights for comparison with histology data.

Acknowledgements

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References

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Figure 1: **Container assembly:** The acrylic sphere is cut in half and the bottom of the plastic cylinder is removed. Both parts are glued together with silicone. The brain is put into the container, placing it upside down as close as possible into the sphere. For better fixation, tissue is put around the brain and plastic cups on top of it. The container is then placed in a bucket and filled with formaldehyde. After 12h of degassing the container is closed within the bucket to avoid entry of air bubbles.

Figure 2: **Left:** Low resolution image acquired with CP mode excitation. B_1 inhomogeneities introduce severe signal drop-outs in the brain. **Right:** A tailored kt-points excitation mitigates the inhomogeneities over the whole brain.

Figure 3: Montage of Ernst angle gradient echo acquisition. Demonstrating the ability to achieve homogeneous contrast without remaining signal voids over the whole brain volume.

Figure 4: ** a-c):** Unprocessed high resolution gradient echo images: Low gray/white matter contrast, as well as bright formaldehyde signal in the background. d): After post-processing image contrast is optimized and the bright background signal almost removed.

Figure 5: Representative slices after applying all post-processing steps: Data fitting, contrast optimization, bias field correction, and image denoising.